
THE GENESIS OF THEORETICAL APPROACHES TO SOCIAL PROTECTION OF THE POPULATION

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8003510>

Kholmurodov Gulom

*In the name of Mirzo Ulugbek
National University of Uzbekistan*

teacher

xolmurodov6994@gmail.com

Annotation.

This article describes the processes of formation of the concept of social protection of the population, the main views of the ancient world, eastern and western scientists regarding the social protection and support of the state's population (citizens).

Key words.

"Avesta", "State", ideal state, "Politics", "Bible", "Qur'an", "Al-jame as-sahih", "City of virtuous people", "Two words about governance treatise", "Social contract", "On the spirit of laws".

When we refer to history to study the concept of social protection of the population, we can see the social policy of the states, the reforms implemented by the state leaders, and the relations of mutual cooperation between the population of the country and the state.

Human development has experienced the process of self-improvement for centuries through the changes that occurred in different periods, in different places and times.

In particular, "Avesta", which appeared in Ancient Khorezm, became a great social, political, spiritual and moral reality as a sacred book of Zoroastrian religion. "In the Avesta", a new stage of human development, the development of the world of imagination and thought, concepts of man, society, state, and social life appeared.

In Zoroastrian teachings, the principle of good thoughts, good words, good deeds (pindori nek, guftori nek, kirdori nek) took the main place. Based on this teaching, if we study the Zoroastrian religion as a social phenomenon, then the relationship between man and society, universe and man has its own (connection) pathos, with its own tone and strict demand. As a result, the religion of

Zoroastrianism promoted the idea of justice, goodness, and goodness to people and brought the way of thinking of mankind from primitive views to a new level[1].

With its philosophical and social essence, the ideas of “Avesta” destroyed the primitive views typical of its time and broke the frozen ideas. Expanded the limits of human thinking. It served as an important resource in creating a new way of thinking, a new attitude, a harmony of faith and goodness. In it, the principle of a well-rounded person, a morally mature person was put forward through a society built on the basis of reason and thinking.

In “Avesta” great attention was paid to social relations between people. We can see this in the ideas of justice, the relationship between women and men, and social responsibility covered in this source.

Issues such as social protection, state management, and the relationship between man and society are widely covered in the teachings of Greek thinkers such as Plato and Aristotle.

In his work called “The State”[2], Plato described in detail his views on how the members of the society should lead a prosperous life. According to him, a perfect, fully formed state should have the following basic qualities. They include such basic qualities as 1) wisdom, 2) courage, 3) patience, 4) justice.

According to the thinker, any society is divided into three classes. The highest class: it consists mainly of sages who rule the state. In the middle is the class: it includes the warriors who protect the state from the disorder that arises in society. Lower class: among them Plato included artisans, farmers and merchants.

In order for his ideal state to be strong, Plato requires these three classes to be brothers. For example, the producers must work for the other two classes, and the military must protect them, and the sages, in turn, order and give instructions to the military to protect them.

It is worth mentioning that Plato's teachings about the state and society have a utopian character, because there is not only consensus but also conflicts among the members of society. In turn, emerging conflicts cause the dynamics of positive or negative changes, despite this, Plato's views greatly contributed to the development of social teachings and theories.

Aristotle is considered to be the Greek thinker who continued Plato's socio-political teachings, and at the same time expressed his opposition to them, who made a great contribution to the world of social thought. Aristotle's treatise “Politics”[3] is a socio-philosophical teaching that reflects the concepts of the state, society and human problems, their social structure, mutual relations, the concept and types of state administration, social inequality, and the rights of citizens.

In his treatise called "Politics", Aristotle paid great attention to the social protection of the population, as well as public administration in its support. In turn, the thinker proposes to study the society by dividing it into three social strata. Aristotle includes the strata of the rich, the middle class, and the poor.

In his opinion, the state should not be ruled by the very rich, because they have acquired wealth unjustly, and therefore are not worthy to rule the state. In addition, all the thoughts of the rich are directed not to achieving common interests, but to maintaining and increasing their wealth.

The poor should not rule the country either, because they have not been able to support themselves through laziness and carelessness. It follows that the poor, who have gained power, look out for themselves first and foremost as much as the rich, they enjoy the privileges of their position, and the state he spends his wealth for his own needs, but does not increase it.

The middle class is of particular importance for the welfare of the state. They have achieved their well-being through honest work, and they also understand well that work depends on the well-being of the state. Because of this, the middle class strives to improve life in the state, they have things to gain and things to lose. Based on this, their policy is reasonable.

Although Aristotle's social teachings are reasonable, the analysis of the population into three strata does not give great results. Because now we can divide the middle class into several groups. For example, the intelligentsia, workers, entrepreneurs, etc. Although their interests and outlook are common in certain aspects, they have different interests and values.

Social protection of the population is widely covered in world religions. We can see it in the Bible[4], which is considered the holy book of Christianity. It highlights the fact that charity is the highest quality of a person, that everyone should give at least 10% of their income to the needs of socially disadvantaged groups, provide shelter to the homeless, and help the poor.

The values of the Christian religion have had a serious impact on human thinking, and new social paradigms have emerged based on its teachings.

Islam is another religion that has greatly influenced the social thinking and values of mankind. As a result of the introduction of Islam into the life of society, special attention was paid to the issues of social protection. In order to meet the needs of the poor and widows, taxes such as zakat, kharaj (tax), and ushr were introduced.

In the holy book of Islam "Holy Qur'an"[5] in Surah Al-Baqarah verse 177, "Turning your faces to the East and the West (your prayer) is not a good thing, but

to Allah, the Last Day, angels, books, believe in the storehouses, those who give from what they love to their relatives, orphans, the needy, the wayfarer, beggars, and the way to free slaves, those who pray and pay the zakat, and those who keep their covenants, and those who persevere in times of hardship and in times of war are good (people). It is they who are faithful (in their faith) and it is they who are pious”.

Muhammad al-Bukhari's "Al-jame as-sahih"[6] (Collection of Reliable Hadiths) Volume 1 Book of Faith Chapter 5. Feeding the hungry is from Islam. The Messenger of Allah, peace and blessings be upon him, asked: "Which qualities are the best in Islam?" They said. "Don't feed the hungry and don't greet those you don't know" and chapter 35. Giving Zakat is Islam. It is said in the Ayat Karim: "People of the Book were commanded to pray to Allah alone, abandon false beliefs, choose the true faith, pray and give zakat”.

Abu Nasr Farabi is considered one of the great thinkers of the Eastern Renaissance, and his work "The City of Virtuous People"[7] contains his socio-philosophical views on society, a just system, what should be just rulers, the existence of the needs necessary for each person to live, people on their own that in order to meet their needs and achieve perfection, they must unite in communities and society, a city where people who do good and beautiful deeds and actions remind each other of each other in order to achieve true happiness is a city of virtuous people; People who help each other are virtuous people.

The beginning of a new era in Western European countries in the 17th-19th centuries led to changes in social life, the development of science and technology, an increase in the standard of living of the population, and the formation of political ideas.

In particular, the English politician John Locke explained in his "Two Treatises on Government"[8] that civil society is based on agreements, that is, the existence of a "Social Contract" for the population to live together comfortably, safely and peacefully. According to him, in the social protection of the population from the arbitrariness of the owners and monarchs, they were given the right to live, the right to freedom, the right to freely dispose of their property, and equal political rights, and they gave people the opportunity to perform their actions independently.

In "On the Spirit of Laws"[9] by the famous French thinker S. L. Montesquieu, laws are divided into two groups, according to which the laws regulating the social protection of the population and fair relations between rulers and citizens in their support are political. rights, legal equality of citizens living in the society, freedoms

based on private property, laws defining mutual relations of citizens as civil rights. He believes that these rights should be protected by the state.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1.Авеста В.С.Соколова. Опыт морфологической транскрипции и перевод / И. А. Смирнова. Подготовка материалов к изданию и редактирование. – СПб: «Наука», 2005 – 544 с. ISBN 5-02-02705 1-2.

2.Платон. Сочинения в четырех томах. Т. 3. Ч. 1 / Под общ. ред. А. Ф. Лосева и В. Ф. Асмуса; Пер. с древнегреч. – СПб: Изд-во С.-Петербур. ун-та; «Изд-во Олега Абышко», 2007. – 752 с. ISBN 978-5-89740-157-4.

3.Политика/Аристотель; пер. с греческого С.А.Жебелева, Т.А.Миллер. – Москва: Издательство АСТ, 2018. – 320 с. (Власть: искусство править миром). ISBN 978-5-17-103306-4.

4.Библия. Книги Священного Писания Ветхого и Нового Завета. Канонические современный русский перевод. Учебное издание москва российское библейское общество. УДК 22.07. ББК 86.37-2 2022. – 1626 с.

5.Qur’oni Karim ma’nolarning tarjima va ta’sviri. Tarjima va ta’svir muallifi Abdulaziz Mansur. “Toshkent Islom Unversiteti” nashriyot-matbaa birlashmasi. 2004 yil.

6.Al-jome as-sahih. 1-jild. Imom Ismoil al-Buxoriy. Arabchadan Zokirjon Ismoil tarjimasini. Qomuslar Bosh tahririyati. Toshkent 1991.

7.Форобий, Абу Наср. Фозил одамлар шаҳри. Абу Наср Форобий / Таржимонлар Абдусодиқ Ирисов, Маҳкам Маҳмудов, Урфон Отажон. Масъул мухаррирлар М.Хайруллаев, М.Жакбаров. – Тошкент: Янги аср авлоди, 2016. – 320 б. ISBN 978-9943-27-613-0. УЎК: 001.6. КБК: 87.3. Ф – 84.

8.Джон Локк. Два трактата о правлении / Дж. Локк; пер. с англ. Е. С. Лагутина, Ю. В. Семенова. – 4-е изд., эл. – 1 файл pdf: 496 с. – Москва; Челябинск: Социум, 2020. – Систем. Требования: Adobe Reader XI либо Adobe Digital Editions 4.5; экран 10. – Текст: электронный.

9.Оригинал: фр. De l’esprit des lois. – Источник: Монтескье Шарль Луи. Избранные произведения / Общ. ред. и вступ. ст. М. П. Баскина – М.: Гослитиздат, 1955.